

Phytochemistry, Pharmacology & Traditional use of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*

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ABSTRACT

Nyctanthes arbor-tristis Linn., commonly known as “Night Jasmine” or “Parijat,” is a highly valued plant in traditional Indian medicine. Belonging to the family Oleaceae, it is recognized for its ornamental beauty and diverse therapeutic properties. The plant is rich in bioactive constituents such as iridoid glycosides, flavonoids, alkaloids, terpenoids, phenolics, and sterols that contribute to its wide range of pharmacological activities. Various parts of the plant—including leaves, flowers, bark, seeds, and roots—have been reported to exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiviral, antimicrobial, hepatoprotective, antidiabetic, antipyretic, & immunomodulatory effects. Traditional systems of medicine like Ayurveda, Siddha, and Unani have utilized *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* in the management of ailments such as malaria, arthritis, chronic fever, sciatica, and respiratory disorders. Recent pharmacological investigations have validated many of these ethnomedicinal claims, highlighting its potential as a source of novel therapeutic agents. This review consolidates available information on the phytochemical composition, pharmacological activities, and traditional applications of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*, thereby emphasizing its significance in modern herbal research and potential for future drug development.

Keywords: Phytochemistry, Pharmacology, *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*

INTRODUCTION

Plant Description: *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* is also known as ‘Night Jasmine’ as its flowers emit a strong & pleasant fragrance during whole night. After midnight & by day break, the flowers start falling. From two Greek Words Nykhta (Night) & Anthos (Flower), *Nyctanthes* has been coined. Meaning of ‘arbortristis’ is ‘the sad tree’.

Fig. No.: 1. Leaves of *Nyctanthes arbortristis*

Nyctanthes arbor-tristis Linn. (NAT), a small divine ornamental tree, is used to pray God across India and is known for its fragrant white flowers. The plant is a well-known traditional Indian medicinal plant also, which in Ayurveda is used for various pharmacological actions such as anti-arthritic, antispasmodic, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antiviral immunostimulant, antidiabetic, antioxidant, hepatoprotective, antimicrobial, anti-pyretic, anthelmintic, antileishmanial, anti-allergic, and CNS depressant. It is an herbal remedy for treating sciatica, malaria, enlargement of spleen and other various infectious and non-infectious diseases. It is also used as blood purifier. *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* in local language is commonly known as Harsinghar, Parijata or night flowering jasmine. The generic name ‘*Nyctanthes*’ came from the Greek words ‘Nykhta’ meaning ‘night’ and ‘anthos’ meaning ‘flower’ while

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the specific name 'arbortristis' means 'the sad tree' because of the dull look of tree during the daytime.¹

Synonyms: *Bruschia macrocarpa* Bertol, *Nyctanthes dentata* Blume, *Nyctanthes tristis* Salisb, *Parilium arbor-tristis* (L.) Gaertn, *Scabrita scabra* L, *Scabrita triflora* L.²

Taxonomy:

- **Kingdom** :Plantae
- **Division** :Magnoliophyta
- **Class** :Magnoliopsida
- **Order** :Lamiales
- **Family** :Oleaceae
- **Genus** :*Nyctanthes*
- **Species** : *arbor-tristis*.²

Vernacular Names:

- **Ayurvedic:** Paarijaata, Shephaali.
- **English:** Tree of Sorrow, Night Jasmine.
- **Sanskrit:** Parijata, Parijatah, Parijataka.
- **Hindi:** Harsingar.
- **Punjabi:** Harsinghar.
- **Unani:** Harasingaar.
- **Siddha:** Pavazha motif.
- **Thai:** Karanikaa.
- **Filipino:** Coral Jasmine.
- **Indonesian:** Sundanese, Javanese .
- **Gujarati:** Jayaparvati, Parijatak .²

It is a terrestrial woody shrub with white flowers having an extraordinarily strong and pleasant fragrance whole night that grows up to 10 meters in height and have a life span of 5-20 years . The plant can be cultivated in tropical and subtropical regions all over the world, from sea-level up to 1500m altitude at the equator . It usually grows in red and black soil with pH of 5.6-7.5 and prefers arid and semi-arid climatic conditions . Flowering generally occur from July to October and flowers are arranged at the tip of branches or in axil of the leaves in cluster of 2-7 flowers together, each flower opening at dusk and falling at dawn. These flowers are fragrant and sessile having 6-8mm long, narrowly campanulate, hairy outside, glabrous inside, ciliated calyx and more than 13mm long, 6-8mm long tube, 5-8 unequally obcordate and cuneate lobed white corolla with an orange-red centre. Two stamens are inserted near the

top of corolla tube and stigma is obscurely bifid. The fruits are flat, compressed, brown heart-shaped to round capsules with two sections each containing a single seed. Seeds are exalbuminous, testa are thick and outer layer of large transparent cells is heavily vascularized while cotyledons are flat, and radicle is inferior. The leaves are rough, hairy, decussately opposite, simple, 6-12 cm long, 2-6.5 cm wide with an entire margin.³

Habitat & Ecology: It is a large shrub & small tree (up to 10 m in height) which is cultivated in tropical widely & all over the world as a subtropical region. It is seen throughout the sub-Himalayan ranges from Chenab to Nepal, Assam, Burma, Bengal, & Godavari southwards. It is also widely distributed in Bangladesh, Indo-Pak subcontinent and South-East Asia, tropical and sub-tropical South East Asia. It grows in the Indo-Malayan region and distributed across Terai tracts as well as Burma and Ceylon. It tolerates moderate shade and is often found as undergrowth in dry deciduous forests. It is also found in Thailand . On rocky ground, dry deciduous forests or at sea level upto 1500 m altitude it can grow . Due to its pleasant & peculiar fragrance , it is cultivated in gardens.⁴

Fig. No.: 2. Flower of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis*

PHYTOCHEMISTRY, PHARMACOLOGY & TRADITIONAL USES

Phytochemistry: Phytosterols, phenolics, tannins, flavonoids, glycosides, and saponins were discovered through phytochemistry analysis of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* leaves, fruits, and seeds. The biggest chemical groups produced by this plant are its secondary metabolites, which include glycosides and alkaloids. In vitro, extracts of the seeds, flowers, and leaves have

antileishmanial, antiviral, antifungal, and immunostimulant properties. A glycoside and two alkaloids, one of which is soluble in water and the other in chloroform, are also present in the bark. Alkaloids, tannins, and glucosides are the main ingredients in its roots. Iridoid glucosides,

arbortrioside A, B, D, and E have been identified from seeds. Phenylpropanoid glucosides are the other two types of glycosides. The *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* flower contains a large amount of mannitol. Flowers contain an essential oil that is a modified diterpenoid nycanthin, flavonoids, and anthocyanins.⁵

Table No.: 1. Phytoconstituents of *Nyctanthes arbor tristis*, Their classes and their Structures

Sl no.	Phytoconstituent	Chemical Class	Parts of plant Constituting the Phytochemicals	Structure of the Phytoconstituent
1	Desrhamnosylverbacoside	Iridoid Glycoside	Leaf	
2	B-sitosterol	Steroid	Leaf, Stem, Seed	
3	Friedeline	Terpenes	Leaf	
4	Lupeol	Terpenes	Leaf	
5	Nicotiflorin	Flavonoid	Leaf	
6	Arbortrioside A, B, C, D & E	Iridoid Glycoside	Seed	 Arbortrioside A

				<p>Arbortristoside B</p>
				<p>Arbortristoside C</p>
				<p>Arbortristoside D</p>
				<p>Arbortristoside E</p>
7	6-trans-cinnamoyl-7-o-acetyl-6 β hydroxyloganin	Iridoid Glycoside	Flower	

8	Arborside C	Iridoid Glycoside	Flower	
9	6 β -hydroxyloganin	Iridoid Glycoside	Flower	
10	Oleanolic acid	Terpenes	Leaf	

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY :

Pharmacological Activity of *Nyctanthes Arbor-Tristis*:

The crude extracts of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* and its various fractions from leaf, bark, root, seed, and oil have all been reported to have biological activity. Different portions of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* have been crudely extracted and utilized in traditional medicine to treat a variety of illnesses. Since the beginning of time, various portions of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* have been used in Ayurveda, Siddha, and Unani systems of medicine. The powdered stem bark is traditionally used as an expectorant, to cure malaria, and to relieve the pain associated with rheumatic joints. The plant has been tested for antihistaminic, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, antiulcer, amoebicidal, anthelmintic, antiparasitic to antidepressants, antiviral, and immunomodulatory properties. It has also been tested for CNS activity (hypnotic, tranquilizing, anesthetic) and for analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, antiulcer, and amoebicidal properties.

Antioxidant Activity : In their research on the plant, Anowar et al. came to the conclusion that *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*'s hydroalcoholic floral extract has antioxidative and protective properties against the oxidative stress of hydrogen peroxide, or H₂O₂. The mild oxidising agent H₂O₂ can cross the cell membrane and enter the cell, where it interacts with the ions Fe²⁺ and Cu²⁺ to produce hydroxyl radicals. These hydroxyl radicals interact with the cell's micro- and macromolecules to further harm the cell and inactivate enzymes by typically oxidising the thiol (-SH) groups. They used H₂O₂ to treat the lymphocytes purified from chicken blood, which reduced cell viability by reducing the antioxidant reduced glutathione (GSH). When the lymphocytes were treated with, there was a substantial 1.22-fold rise in the amount of GSH. ⁶

Anticancer Activity : Khatune et al. discovered petroleum ether, chloroform, and ethyl acetate extracts of flowers to demonstrate substantial cytotoxic activity, which is how *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*'s anticancer properties were initially discovered. In comparison to 5- fluorouracil, stem

bark methanolic extract has recently been found to exhibit substantial anticancer effect against Dalton's ascetic lymphoma in Swiss albino rats.⁷

Antiviral Activity : The ethanolic extract, n-butanol fractions, and two isolated pure chemicals, arbortristoside C, have been obtained from the *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* and have strong inhibitory effect against Semliki Forest virus, encephalomyocarditis virus (EMCV) (SFV). At daily doses of 125 mg/kg body weight, the in-vivo ethanolic extract and the n-butanol fraction protected EMCV-infected mice against SFV by 40 and 60%, respectively.⁸

Antidiabetic Activity : In comparison to diabetic controls, oral administration of chloroform leaf and flower extracts and 50% ethanolic leaf extracts significantly increases superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT) levels and significantly decreases liver lacto peroxidase (LPO), serum levels of SGPT, SGOT, alkaline phosphatase, cholesterol, and triglyceride levels. When administered to streptozotocinnicotinamide -induced diabetic rats, the stem bark's ethanol extract also exhibited notable anti-diabetic efficacy. In a dose-dependent way, the extract decreases blood glucose levels.⁹

Anti-Allergy Activity : A water-soluble fraction of the alcoholic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor -tristis* leaves provided considerable protection against the onset of hypoxia in guinea pigs exposed to histamine aerosol. In *Nyctanthes arbor- tristis*, arbortristosides A and C have been found to have anti-allergic properties.¹⁰

Antifungal Activity : *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium*, and *Aspergillus flavus*, the three most common clinical pathogenic fungus, were tested for antifungal activity in various areas of the *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* plant. Collected and dried fresh and mature leaves, seeds, stems, bark, and flowers were then extracted using distilled water, methanol, and chloroform. By using the well diffusion method, the antifungal activity of the extracts was evaluated in terms of the "zone of inhibition" of fungal growth. The findings showed that only a distilled water extract of *Nyctanthes arbor- tristis*'s stem and bark had antifungal action against *A. niger*, but a chloroform extract of its leaves had antifungal activity exclusively

against *A. flavus*. The research revealed that methanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*'s leaves, stem, and bark displayed the strongest antifungal effectiveness against both *Aspergillus*¹¹.

Antifilarial Activity : Against the typical floral vector *Culex quinquefasciatus*, the chloroform extract of the flowers and a purified chemical isolated from *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* plant exhibit larvicidal activity.¹²

Antibacterial Activity : The main factor contributing to early mortality worldwide is infectious diseases. A wide range of pathogens have the ability to resist antimicrobial drugs, and multiple drug resistance is becoming more prevalent in a variety of different organisms, including *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermis*, *Salmonella typhi*, and *Salmonella paratyphi A*. According to a study, a methanolic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor -tristis* leaves had MIC values between 1 and 8 mg/ml and shown strong antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermis*, *Salmonella typhi*, and *Salmonella paratyphi A*. The extracts' minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and zone of inhibition were calculated, and the results were compared to those of the common medications fluconazole and ciprofloxacin.¹³

Antihistaminic Activity : The alcoholic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor -tristis* leaves' water solubility (4.0 and 8.0g/kg oral) strongly shields guinea pigs from histamine aerosol-induced hypoxia (2% at 300 mm Hg). *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* contains the anti-allergic compounds arbortristosid A and arbortristosid C.¹⁴

Antipyretic Activity : Fever is a complicated physiological reaction that is brought on by infectious or aseptic stimuli and results in elevated body temperature. This is caused by an increase in prostaglandin E (2) concentration in specific brain regions, which then affects the rate at which neurons in the hypothalamus that regulate temperature fire. Antipyretics are medications that lower a high body temperature. Albino rats were used to test the effects of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* on both healthy body temperature and pyrexia brought on by yeast. At a dose of 200 mg/kg, the whole plant extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* demonstrated considerable antipyretic efficacy by lowering both resting body

temperature and increased temperature induced by yeast in a dose-dependent manner. Additionally, it was discovered that the effect of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* dosage whole plant extract was comparable to that of paracetamol.¹⁵

Anxiolytic Activity : Adult Albino rats and Wister mice were used to test the hydroalcoholic extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* leaves for its ability to reduce anxiety using a variety of models, including the elevated zero maze, elevated plus maze, open field exploratory behaviour, novelty-induced suppressed feeding test, and social interaction test. Rats were administered the extract orally in dosages of 250 and 500 mg/kg, and the results indicated a dose-dependent substantial increase in open field ambulation, rearing, self-grooming, and activity in the centre, demonstrating *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*'s anxiolytic activity.¹⁶

Hepatoprotective Activity : *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* ethanolic leaf extract guards against rat hepatotoxicity brought on by carbon tetrachloride. In order to conduct this study, rats were pretreated with extract (1000 mg/kg body weight/day, orally for 7 days) before receiving a single dosage of CCl₄ (1.0 mg/kg, subcutaneously). Under pentobarbitone anaesthesia (350 mg/kg i.p), blood samples were taken from the abdominal aorta 48 hours following CCl₄ treatment (9 days). As a reference standard, silymarin (70mg/kg body weight/day, p.o. for 7 days) was employed. In this investigation, silymarin and the leaf extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* were found to protect against (CCl₄)-induced increases in liver weight and volume and to restore all serum and liver parameters to their original levels while also preventing weight loss.¹⁷

Anti-Inflammatory Activity : Acute and subacute antiinflammatory action was found in the aqueous extract of the entire plant, the alcoholic extract of the stem and seeds, and the water-soluble component of the alcoholic extract of the leaves of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*. Various phlogistic agents, such as carrageenan, formalin, histamine, 5-hydroxytryptamine, and hyaluronidase, are used in inflammatory models to assess the acute anti-inflammatory activity. In both the granuloma pouch and the cotton pellet tests, it was discovered that *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* significantly inhibited the formation of granulation tissue in the sub-acute

animals. Additionally, it has been discovered that *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* inhibits the inflammation brought on by the pure tuberculin reaction and Freund's adjuvant arthritis immunological techniques.¹⁸

Anti-Arthritic Activity : An autoimmune disease of the synovial joints, arthritis is characterised by persistent inflammation that causes pain, inflammation of the synovial joints, pannus development, cartilage rupture, reduced movement, and disability. Arthritis is typically brought on by inflammatory mediators and infections. Today, nonbiologic disease modifying antirheumatic medications (DMARD) like methotrexate, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAID) like piroxicam, biological treatments like IL-6, IL-1, and TNF-inhibitors, and glucocorticoids like methyl prednisolone and triamcinolone are used to treat arthritis. The first-line treatment for rheumatoid arthritis is NSAIDs, which efficiently reduce inflammation, discomfort, and stiffness in the joints but have unfavourable side effects such stomach ulcers, bleeding, dyspepsia, and an increased risk of cardiovascular issues.¹⁹

Anti-Ulcerogenic Activity : One of the most common gastrointestinal illnesses, peptic ulcer, results from an imbalance between defensive and offensive factors, namely mucusbicarbonate secretion and prostaglandins. Offensive forces include acid, pepsin, *H. pylori*, and bile salts. The two main treatment modalities for gastric ulcer condition are a decrease in stomach acid production and gastric mucosal protection. There have been claims that the *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* compounds arbortristoside-A and 7-O-trans-cinnamoyl-6-hydroxyloganin have anti-ulcerogenic and ulcer-healing properties. These two help to speed up gastric ulcer healing while also preventing the development of irritant-induced stomach ulcers.²⁰

Anti-Asthmatic Activity : One of the famous medicinal plants is *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn (Oleaceae). It is frequently referred to as "Night Jasmine." Our goal was to investigate the plant's antiasthmatic potential using appropriate models because the herb is traditionally used to treat asthma and cough. By seeing how different plant extracts

affected mice with catalepsy brought on by clonidine and haloperidol, researchers were able to test the extracts for antihistaminic efficacy. The effect of the extracts on milk-induced leukocytosis and eosinophilia allowed researchers to examine the antiallergic effect. Mice were used to study the extracts' ability to stabilise mast cells. Results indicated that compared to other extracts, petroleum ether extract exhibited superior antihistaminic, antiallergic, and mast cell stabilisation properties. We found that the petroleum ether extract included - sitosterol, which has antiasthmatic properties.²¹

Antileishmanial Activity : Iridoid glucosides, arbortristosides A, B, and C, as well as 6-b-hydroxyloganin, have all been linked to *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*' anti-leishmanial action. Both in vitro and in vivo anti-leishmanial efficacy was shown by the arbortristosides A, B, C, and 6- betahydroxy-loganin against amastigotes in macrophage cultures and hamster test systems, respectively. ²²

Anti-Spasmodic Activity : Utilizing guinea pig ileum preparation against the spasmodic agent acetylcholine, *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*' antispasmodic activity was evaluated. Based on the reduction of acetyl choline's contractile impact by various extract dilutions, the antispasmodic efficacy of several plant parts' ethanolic extracts was calculated; flower and seed extracts were the most effective. Less than 16 mg of piperazine citrate, 72 mg of flower extract and 90 mg of seed extract reduced the contractile response to 0.0002 mg of acetylcholine.²³

Anti-Amnesic Activity : Neurological disorders, which include diverse mental conditions like depression, panic attacks, phobias, generalized anxiety, obsessive- compulsive and post-traumatic disorders, are more prevalent in the population ageing between 18 and 60 years. Alzheimer's disease is the most prevalent of these degenerative diseases and is characterized by age-related deterioration in cognitive and learning difficulties as well as neuronal loss, inflammation, and memory loss. The pathogenesis of Alzheimer's disease is brought on by the hippocampus region of the brain's elevated oxidative stress and cholinergic system malfunction. ²⁴

Anti-Anemic Activity : The ethanolic extracts of the plant's flowers, barks, seeds, and leaves were subjected to a haematological analysis, and the results revealed a dose-dependent increase in the haemoglobin content and red blood cell count in rats. In anaemic rats, the extracts also prevent the hemogram profile from deteriorating.²⁵

CNS Depressant Activity : The onset and duration of sleep were significantly and dose-dependently prolonged by the leaves, flowers, seeds, and barks (600 mg/kg) of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*, which were also found to decrease dopamine and increase serotonin levels. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that the CNS depressant activity of the ethanol extracts of seeds, leaves, and flowers may be caused by the decrease in dopamine and increase in serotonin level.²⁶

Hypoglycemic and Hypolipidemic Activity : Millions of individuals worldwide suffer with diabetes mellitus, a serious illness. Because diabetes has a tendency to raise blood levels of low- density lipoprotein cholesterol and lower levels of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, which cause coronary occlusions and blockages, it is crucial to maintain both blood glucose and lipid levels in people with diabetes. Plants are being explored as an alternative because it has been determined that the current method of treating diabetes with synthetic hypoglycaemic drugs may have unfavourable effects that result in hypoglycemia, gastrointestinal problems, renal toxicity, and hepatotoxicity. The hypoglycaemic and hypolipidemic effects of various doses of boiled aqueous extract of fresh *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* flowers were tested in mice. Mice were given doses of the extract of 200, 500, and 750 mg/kg.²⁷

Wound Healing Activity : Wistar albino rats were used by Matadeen et al., 2011, to assess *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*'s ability to heal wounds. For 16 days, the rats received 2% weight/weight *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* methanolic extract treatment. Both incision and excision wounds were observed to take around 16 days to totally epithelize before the wounds were fully healed. It was determined that *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* extract at a dose of 300 mg per kilogramme can be

used as a successful treatment for both types of wounds.²⁸

Antimalarial Activity : Study conducted on 120 malaria patients. In 92 (76.7%) individuals, the condition was healed within 7 days after receiving a fresh paste made from medium-sized *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* leaves administered three times daily for 7–10 days. While the remaining 8 patients did not respond to the medication, another 20 patients were cured within 10 days. There were no serious negative effects and the paste was well tolerated. *Anopheles stephensi* larvae are killed by methanol and chloroform extracts of leaves when tested against three major mosquito vectors, *Aedes aegypti*, *Culex quinquefasciatus*, and *Anopheles stephensi*, with LC50 values of 244.4 and 747.7 ppm, respectively.²⁹

Anticholinesterase Activity : In mice, the aqueous extract of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* increased acetylcholinesterase activity; it counteracts malathion's suppression of this enzyme. The brain showed the higher effects. It has already been documented that isolated rabbit ileum contractions caused by acetylcholine have weak anti-muscarinic effect.³⁰

Antiparasitic Activity : Trypanocidal activity at a concentration of 1000 g/ml has been reported for a crude 50% ethanolic extract of the leaves. According to in vivo research, the extract considerably increased the time that *Trypanosoma evansi*-infected mice survived by exerting antitrypanosomal activities at doses of 300 and 1000 mg/Kg. It is also stated that when the extract-based therapy is stopped, the parasitemia worsens and the test animals succumb to it, killing them. Infected hamsters with *Leishmania donovani* also showed strong anti-leishmanial activity in response to *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* extract. It has been discovered that the 50% ethanolic extracts of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*' seeds, leaves, roots, flowers, and stem can cure *Entamoeba histolytica* infections in rat cecum. The extracts weren't functional in vitro, though.³¹

Antiaggressive Activity : Fresh juice extracted from the plant's leaves was discovered to have antimalarial properties. It has been demonstrated that the 50% ethanolic extract of the plant's seeds, leaves, roots, flowers, and stem has antiamebic and antiallergic

qualities. The plant's leaf extract demonstrated anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antipyretic, and allergic effects. According to reports, the plant's leaves, seeds, and flowers have immunostimulant properties. It has been demonstrated that the ethanolic extract's water-soluble fraction has sedative, antihistamine, purgative, and tumour necrosis-depleting properties. It was discovered that the arbortristiside extracted from the seeds had anticancer action.³²

Anti- Trypanosomal Potential Antitrypanosomal Activity : Both in vitro and in vivo tests were conducted to assess the potential of a crude 50% ethanol extract of leaves from *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*. The extract was trypanocidal at the highest tested concentration (1000 g/ml). According to in vivo research, the extract dramatically increased the survival time of *Trypanosoma evansi*-infected mice when administered intraperitoneally at doses of 300 and 1000 mg/kg. However, as soon as the extract therapy was stopped, the parasitemia grew and led to the death of the test animals.³³

Membrane Stabilizing Activity : Anglican Ag-NY1 is a carotenoid that was isolated from the orange-colored tubular calyx of flowers in a study on *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*. Comparing the compound's membrane stabilizing activity to the comparable glycoside crossing revealed that it was effective.³⁴

Sedative Activity : Rats were used to test the sedative effects of a hot infusion of the flowers. In this experiment, male rats showed dose-dependent conscious sedative behavior while female rats showed no such behavior. Even at the greatest dose, neither blood glucose levels nor muscle strength or cardio *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* were impacted by these doses. However, there was a marked reduction in glucose absorption from the small intestine. The antioxidant and membrane stabilizing properties of the extract were partly blamed for the sedation.³⁵

TRADITIONAL USE

Traditional Use of Flowers : The flowers are harvested to make garlands & for religious offerings. The Buddhist monks whose orange robes were given their colour by this flower are credited with invention of the practise of using the orange heart to dye silk and cotton. Hindu folklore considers Parijata to be one of

the five wish-fulfilling the Devaloka trees. It is known that several portions of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn diseases by the Indian tribal people using its use in Ayurveda, Siddha, and Unani medication delivery systems. Flowers The blossoms are used as an astringent for the bowels, a stomachic, and in the treatment of piles and numerous skin conditions, as an antibilious, expectorant, hair tonic, and in the administration for ophthalmic reasons. The flowers' vivid orange corolla tubes include.³⁶

Traditional Use of Leaves : The bitter leaves have laxative, diaphoretic, diuretic properties. The leaf juice is used to cure a variety of conditions, including stubborn sciatica, rheumatism, loss of appetite, piles, liver and biliary problems, chronic fever, malarial fever, and roundworms and threadworms in children. In Ayurvedic medicine the leaves are frequently used to cure malaria and rheumatoid arthritis. The foliage is also used for dry coughs for fungal skin infections. Young leaves are employed both in female tonics and in reducing gynecological issues . *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* leaves Linn is widely employed for the treatment of a variety of illnesses like sciatica, persistent fever, intestinal worm infestations, rheumatism, and as a laxative, diaphoretic, and for the treatment of cough, leaf juice is combined with honey and administered three times a day. For the treatment of fever, high blood pressure, and diabetes, leaf paste is given with honey. The juice from the leaves is used as a laxative, diaphoretic, antidote to reptile venoms, digestive, somewhat bitter tonic, and diuretic. The spleen can also be enlarged with leaves. The leaf juice is used to treat rheumatism, piles, chronic fever, stubborn sciatica, intestinal worms, liver disorders, biliary disorders, loss of appetite, and fever with rigours. Leaf juice has cholagogue, laxative, and mildly bitter tonic properties. Children are fed it with less sugar as a treatment for digestive problems. uretic, among other conditions.³⁷

Traditional Use Of Stem: The powdered stem bark is traditionally used as an expectorant, to treat malaria, and to relieve rheumatoid joint discomfort. The bark is used to cure bronchitis and snakebites. For the treatment of malaria, the stem bark is pounded with *Piper longum* and *Zingiber officinale*, then the mixture is cooked in water and consumed for two days. When combined with *Arjuna* bark, the resulting

paste is applied to the body to cure internal wounds and shattered bones in joints . The bark is used to cure snakebites and bronchitis. Traditional uses for its roots include anthelmintics.³⁸

Traditional Use of Seeds : The seed powder is used as an anthelmintic, to treat alopecia, and to treat scurvy. It works well for bilious fevers and is both an expectorant and an antibilious. The powdered seeds are used to treat skin conditions, piles, and scurfy affections of the scalp.³⁹

CONCLUSION

Nyctanthes arbor-tristis has tremendous potential pharmacological activities. Pharmacological activities are widely distributed in medicinal plant of and it is revealed as important of herbal and ayurvedic pathway for effective treatment of various diseases. Various researchers have reported that the leaves contain various phytoconstituents which having potent antioxidant activity. So ,the leaves extract can be used to check antioxidant properties by In vitro as well as In vivo assay for future work.

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